

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ACCELERATION BENEFICIARY AGREEMENT

Revision: v.1.0

Agreement Number	COVID-X-OC1-2021/___
Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

Contracting parties

F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED (F6S), established in 39 Fitzwilliam Place Dublin 2, D02ND6, DUBLIN, Ireland, VAT number: IE3629141FH, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Nuno VARANDAS, acting as an agent of F6S with powers delegated to sign COVID-X contracts. Hereinafter referred as the “Contractor”

UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (UPM), established in CALLE RAMIRO DE MAEZTU 7 EDIFICIO RECTORADO, 28040 MADRID, Spain , VAT number: ESQ2818015F, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by [UPM please provide], [Position,UPM please provide], legal representative of UPM.

Hereinafter referred as the “Treasurer”

Of the one part,

[COMPANY_NAME], a Company organized under the laws of [COUNTRY], established in [LEGAL_ADDRESS], with VAT number [VAT_NUMBER], duly represented by [LEGAL_REPRESENTATIVE], [LEGAL_REPRESENTATIVE_POSITION],

Hereinafter referred as the “Beneficiary”

Hereinafter collectively referred as the “Contracting Parties”

HAVE AGREED to the following terms and conditions including those in the following Annexes, which form an integral part of this COVID-X Acceleration Process 1 Beneficiary Agreement (hereinafter referred as the “Contract”):

General Provisions

The European Commission (hereinafter referred as the “EC”) and the Contractor, as a member of the COVID-X consortium, have signed the Grant Agreement no 101016065 for the implementation of the project

“COVID eXponential Programme” (Acronym: COVID-X) within the framework of the Programme H2020-SCI-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2-CNECT.

The Beneficiary has received the favourable resolution by the external evaluators and therefore is entitled to receive funding and services according to the terms and conditions set out under this Beneficiary Agreement and in accordance with the Annex 2: Guidelines for Applicants. This Contract aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties.

The Funding received by the Beneficiary is property of the EC. The Contractor and Treasurers are mere holders and managers of the funds.

Article 1 – Entry into force & Termination of the contract

1.1 Entry into force

This Contract shall enter into force on the day of its signature by the last Contracting Party. However, late signature of the contract by any of the contracting parties will not affect the execution schedule of the sub-project. The Contractor shall sign this contract, only after all of the following documents have been received from the Beneficiary:

- The original signed Declaration of Honour (as given in Annex 4 of this Contract);
- *SME Declaration* form (as given in Annex 5 of this Contract);
- Copy of ID-card or Passport of legal representative(s) of the SME;
- Copy of the original Extract of SME registration;
- Proof of VAT registration;
- Bank Information Form (as given in Annex 6 of this Contract).

All documents shall be sent to the Contractor first via email to the following address: administrative@covid-x.eu, while the Annexes 1, 2, 3 and 3.1 of this Contract will also be sent as originals, via regular mail, to the following address:

UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (COVID-X Team)
CALLE RAMIRO DE MAEZTU 7 EDIFICIO RECTORADO
28040 MADRID
Spain

The Beneficiary is solely responsible for the accuracy of all data provided to the Contractor.

1.2 Contract Termination

This Contract terminates in the event of unjustified withdraw by the Beneficiary of the current fulfilment of its Contract obligations. “Unjustified withdraw” covers any situation out of “Force Majeure” qualification which determines the absence of performance of the Beneficiary contractual obligations. In this particular case, it entitles the Contractor the right to claim the Beneficiary the full refund of all payments made to the Beneficiary up to date.

Article 2 – Obligations and Responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary are defined in detail in the Annex 2 - Guidelines for Applicants.

Additionally, the Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the Project. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Contractor without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

Article 3 – Breach of Contractual obligations

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, the Contractor reserves the right to claim the Beneficiary the full refund of all payments made to the Beneficiary up to date. The breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary shall be determined by the COVID-X Consortium or COVID-X Project Coordinator. Not attending the Event (unless in the case of Force Majeure) or attending the Event in a manner which intentionally disrupts the Event, shall be deemed as breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary. The provision of false or misleading declarations by the Beneficiary or any unsolved situation of conflict of interest also constitute examples of breach of contractual obligations by the Beneficiary.

For British applicants: Please be aware that eligibility criteria must be complied with for the entire duration of the grant. If the United Kingdom withdraws from the EU during the grant period without concluding an agreement with the EU ensuring in particular that British applicants continue to be eligible, you will cease to receive EU funding (while

continuing, where possible, to participate) or be required to leave the project.

Article 4 – Financial contribution and financial provisions

4.1 Maximum financial contribution

The maximum financial contribution to be granted by the Contractor to the Beneficiary shall not exceed the amount of:

- One Hundred Thousand Euros for SMEs (100,000€)
- Fifty Thousand Euros for Healthcare providers (50,000€).

4.2. Distribution of the financial contribution

The financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary shall be calculated and distributed in accordance with the provisions of the Annex 2: Guidelines for Applicants.

In any case, the financial grant to be paid will always be subject to:

- A favourable resolution by the external evaluators and COVID-X project responsible for assessing the Project in each of the phases;
- Reception and acceptance of the relevant Financial Statement (F1, F2 and F3) of the beneficiary;
- The Beneficiary Bank Account (Annex 6) matches the Financial Statement Bank Account;
- The availability of funds in TREASURER bank account during the relevant payment period;
- Payments to the Beneficiary will be made by the Treasurer. In particular:
 - The Treasurer reserves the right to withhold the payments in case the Beneficiary does not fulfil with its obligations and tasks as per Annex 2 - Guidelines for Applicants;
 - Banking and transaction costs charged by any of the banks related to the handling of any financial resources made available to the Beneficiary by the Treasurer shall be covered by the holder of the bank account which originated the cost. This means that the Treasurer bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank and the Beneficiary bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank.;
- Payments will be released no later than thirty (30) natural days after the notification by the Contractor;

- The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this financial contribution.

4.3. Payments schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant phase of the Project as per the Guidelines for Applicants (Annex 2).

The Beneficiary is entitled to receive exclusively those payments allocated to each specific stage of the Project provided that the conditions under Article 4.2 are met.

Article 5 – Right and obligations related to background

5.1 Agreement on background

The beneficiaries must identify and agree (in writing) on the background for the action ('agreement on background').

'Background' means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that:

- (a) is held by the parties before they acceded to the Agreement, and
- (b) is needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

5.2 Data provided by COVID-X Healthcare Providers

The data made available by the Health Care Providers in technical infrastructure developed by COVID-X is owned by the generating party and, in the context of this agreement is considered background.

5.3 Services, products and data provided by sub grantees

Services and products owned by third parties developed prior entering the acceleration programme are considered background.

The data made available by the third party Health Care Providers in technical infrastructure developed by COVID-X is owned by the generating party and, in the context of this agreement is considered background.

Annex 8 to the Sub-Grant agreement identifies all the background that third parties bring to the project, including but not limited to, a description of the TRL level of the product.

Article 6 — Access rights to background

6.1 Exercise of access rights — Waiving of access rights — No sub-licensing

To exercise access rights, this must first be requested in writing ('request for access').

'Access rights' means rights to use results or background under the terms and conditions laid down in this Agreement.

Waivers of access rights are not valid unless in writing.

Unless agreed otherwise, access rights do not include the right to sub-license.

6.2 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for implementing their own tasks under the action

The beneficiaries must give each other access — on a royalty-free basis — to background needed to implement their own tasks under the action, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement —:

(a) informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel), or

(b) agreed with the other beneficiaries that access would not be on a royalty-free basis.

6.3 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for exploiting their own results

The beneficiaries must give each other access — under fair and reasonable conditions — to background needed for exploiting their own results, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement — informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel).

'Fair and reasonable conditions' means appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged.

Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

6.4 Access rights for affiliated entities

Unless otherwise agreed in the agreement, access to background must also be given — under fair and reasonable conditions (see above; Article 6.3) and unless it is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel) — to affiliated entities established in an EU Member State or ‘associated country’, if this is needed to exploit the results generated by the beneficiaries to which they are affiliated.

Unless agreed otherwise (see above; Article 6.1), the affiliated entity concerned must make the request directly to the beneficiary that holds the background.

Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

Article 7 — Ownership of results

7.1 Ownership by the beneficiary that generates the results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them.

‘Results’ means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

7.2 Joint ownership by several beneficiaries

Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if:

- (a) they have jointly generated them and
 - (b) it is not possible to:
 - (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or
 - (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection
- (see Article 27).

The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (‘joint ownership agreement’), to ensure compliance with their obligations under this Agreement.

Unless otherwise agreed in the joint ownership agreement, each joint owner may grant non-exclusive licences to third parties to exploit jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:

- (a) at least 45 days advance notice and
- (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

Once the results have been generated, joint owners may agree (in writing) to apply another regime than joint ownership (such as, for instance, transfer to a single owner (see Article 30) with access rights for the others).

7.3 Rights of third parties (including personnel)

If third parties (including personnel) may claim rights to the results, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it complies with its obligations under the Agreement.

If a third party generates results, the beneficiary concerned must obtain all necessary rights (transfer, licences or other) from the third party, in order to be able to respect its obligations as if those results were generated by the beneficiary itself.

If obtaining the rights is impossible, the beneficiary must refrain from using the third party to generate the result

Article 8 – Liability of the Beneficiary

Neither the Contractor nor the EC can be held liable for any acts or omissions of the Beneficiary in relation to this Contract. At the same time, the Beneficiary is responsible for any act or omission that causes damage to the Contractor, the Data Provider, and/or the EC in relation to this Contract.

The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that their acts within the framework of this Contract do not infringe third parties' rights. There is no joint liability between the Contracting Parties.

Article 9 – Confidentiality

With respect to all information of whatever nature or form as is disclosed between the Contracting Parties in connection with the Project and identified in writing as confidential, the terms of this Article shall apply. The Contracting Parties agree that such information is communicated on a confidential basis and its disclosure may be prejudicial to the owner of the information.

Article 10 – Force Majeure

“Force Majeure” shall mean, any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Contracting Parties control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Agreement, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable in spite of the exercising all due diligence.

Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as force majeure.

The Contracting Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to force majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.

No Contracting Party shall be considered to be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such breach is caused by Force Majeure. A Contracting Party will notify the other Contracting Party of any Force Majeure as soon as possible. In case the Beneficiary is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within 10 (ten) days after such notification, the Contractor will decide accordingly including the termination of the Contract.

Article 11 – Information and communication

Any publicity made by the Beneficiary in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author’s views and that the Contractor, COVID-X consortium or EC are not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The Contractor, COVID-X consortium and EC shall be authorized to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the Beneficiary;
- contact address of the Beneficiary;
- the general purpose of the project;

- the amount of the financial contribution of the EC.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorizations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the Contractor, COVID-X Consortium or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly substantiated request by the Contractor on behalf of the Beneficiary, the EC may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

Article 12 – Data protection

12.1. General Data Protection Regulation

The Contracting Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specified purposes and adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed.

The Beneficiary will use and process the data only for the purposes of this Contract and during the length of the Contract. Any unauthorised use is forbidden. In any event, neither the Contractor nor the Data Provider will be held responsible for any abusive use of data incurred into by the Beneficiary.

The Beneficiary shall not to try to re-identify anonymised data. In the event that re-identification occurs, the Beneficiary commits not to use such data. The Beneficiary shall delete, at the end of this Contract, the data to which the Beneficiary has been granted access during the incubation process, except where an agreement is entered into with the Data Provider.

12.2 National and local laws

Current national and local laws and regulations that may apply where the Validation Pilot will be carried out. Likewise, they will have to observe the guidelines established for this purpose by the European Data Protection Committee and the Control Authorities in the matter of data protection of the respective countries.

12.3 COVID-X Guideline

Guidelines received from the COVID-X consortium, such as the Project Security Policy or those included in the anonymization guide, among others, will be compulsory for the participants.

12.4. New data produced

The Beneficiary acknowledges that he/she will be the “data controller” of any new dataset of piece of personal information that the Beneficiary may produce in the course of the COVID-X project.

Article 13 – Regulations on biomedical research

The project is subject to the European Union regulations on biomedical research and clinical trials.

The beneficiary must take all relevant measures to assure compliance for the entire duration of the project in particular with :

- Regulation (EU) 536/2014 of the European Parliament and Council of April 16th, 2014 on clinical trials of medicinal products for human use (which repeals the Directive 2001/20/EC)
- Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and Council of April 5th, 2017 on medical devices (amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC)
- National and local laws and regulations that may be applicable where the Pilot Validation will be carried out.

Article 14 – Financial audits and controls

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the Project and up to five years after the end of the COVID-X project (foreseen for 31 December 2021), arrange for financial audits to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF), on the Beneficiary. The audit procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC. Such audits may cover financial, systemic and other aspects (such as accounting and management principles) relating to the proper execution of the Grant Agreement. They shall be carried out on a confidential basis.

The Beneficiary shall make available directly to the EC all detailed information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, with a view to verifying that the Grant Agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions and that costs have been charged in compliance with it. This information and data must be precise, complete and effective.

The Beneficiary shall keep the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies – including electronic copies - of all documents relating to the Contract until 2026. These shall be made available to the EC where requested during any audit under the Grant Agreement.

In order to carry out these audits, the Beneficiary shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the Beneficiary's offices, to its computer data, to its accounting data and to all the information needed to carry out those audits, including information on individual salaries of persons involved in the project. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot at the moment of the audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

On the basis of the findings made during the financial audit, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The EC may decide not to take into account observations conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

On the basis of the conclusions of the audit, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules. In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the EC in order to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

Article 15 – Amendments

Amendments or changes to this Contract shall be made in writing and signed by the duly authorized representative of the Contracting Parties. Nevertheless, In the event the EC modifies the conditions, the Contractor will amend the Contract accordingly.

Article 16 – Language

This contract is drawn up in English, language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings and processes relative thereto.

Article 17 – Applicable Law

This Contract shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium.

Article 18 – Settlement of disputes

If the Contracting Parties are unable to resolve a dispute amicably, such dispute will be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by three (3) arbitrators in Brussels. Each of the Contracting Parties to the dispute shall appoint one (1) arbitrator and the three (3) arbitrators so appointed shall elect the presiding arbitrator. Should a Party to the dispute which should appoint an arbitrator fails to do so within fourteen (14) days of the delivery of the written notice to do so from the other Party to the dispute or should the appointed arbitrators fail to reach agreement on the presiding arbitrator within fourteen (14) days after their appointment, such arbitrator shall be appointed in accordance with the Rules upon request of any of the Parties to the dispute.

The seat of arbitration shall be Brussels.

The Contracting Parties agree that the language of the arbitration, including oral hearings, written evidence and correspondence, shall be English.

A duly rendered arbitration award shall be final and binding on the Contracting Parties to the dispute. Each Contracting Party to the arbitration conducted in accordance with this section hereof shall bear its own expenses incurred in connection with such arbitration, including fees of its legal counsels. All other costs and expenses shall be apportioned between the Contracting Parties to the arbitration in accordance with the decision of the arbitrators.

Nothing in this Contract shall limit the Contracting Parties right to seek injunctive relief or to enforce an arbitration award in any applicable competent court of law.

AS WITNESS:

The Contracting Parties have caused this Contract to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives in three (3) copies:

<p>For F6S (the Contractor) Digitally Signed by Mr Nuno VARANDAS Signature</p> <p>Done at London</p>	<p>For UPM (Treasurer), established in CALLE RAMIRO DE MAEZTU 7 EDIFICIO RECTORADO, 28040 MADRID, SPAIN [UPM Name of legal representative], [UPM Position of legal representative] Signature</p> <p>Done at Madrid</p>
<p>For [SME] (the Beneficiary) Mr/Ms [NAME SURNAME] [POSITION_IN_COMPANY] Signature</p> <p>Done at _____ on DD/MM/2020</p>	

Annexes
